

MAKING DAEGU:

Towards a Fully Circular Metropolis in South Korea

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ABSTRACT

The "Manufacturing Daegu" project, developed by RMIT Architecture in 2023, investigates the methodology and strategies necessary for transforming Daegu, South Korea, into a fully circular city. The project hypothesises and envisions a self-sufficient urban environment where production, consumption, and recycling processes are contained within the city's boundaries. This challenges traditional models of urban development that depend on external resources, leading to environmental degradation and economic vulnerability. The methodology focuses on speculative design, employing architectural and urban planning strategies to explore the spatial implications of a circular economy. By asking, "What if everything consumed in Daegu is made in Daegu?" the project pushes the boundaries of urban sustainability. Key metrics like the "Ecological Footprint" are used to evaluate the land required to support the city's population, highlighting the unsustainability of current consumption patterns and emphasizing the need for a shift towards localized production. The design approach emphasizes increased urban density, integrating production systems directly into the city's core to reduce the ecological footprint. The methodology demonstrates how cities can become self-sufficient by rethinking spatial organization, localizing production, and efficiently using resources, offering a framework for sustainable, resilient urban development.

1. INTRODUCTION

"Manufacturing Daegu" is a 2023 RMIT Architecture design studio project which explores the spatial implications for transforming Daegu, South Korea, into a fully circular city. It is a case study in which such a city would see all essential goods and resources produced, consumed, and recycled within the city's own boundaries. "Circular urbanism" is a radical departure from current global production models, in which cities depend on vast external networks of production and transport for their resources and which contribute significantly to environmental degradation through the scale of those systems. A core question of the design project asks: "What might the city look like if everything consumed in Daegu is made in Daegu?" This question stretches and blurs the boundaries of urban planning, sustainability, and architectural design by imagining a self-sufficient city with the goal of addressing both ecological and economic challenges facing all cities. It assumes that to radically decarbonise a city, a key tool, among others is to reduce reliance on long supply chains and extreme consumption patterns. Bringing production closer to urban consumption not only reduces the burden of enormous transport of goods and waste, it also triggers the rethinking of manufacturing at a local scale. This project is a highly speculative case study with the aim of imagining moves toward circularity, and of implicating the spatial form of a city in such questions, through design. The project acknowledges the complexity of quantifying the impact of global supply logistics or of the viability of its complete (circular) reverse but does assume the benefits of transformations toward that goal, both for the carbon footprint of a city and for its urban form. The project recognises certain unique conditions for Daegu in relation to this question while also treating it as a case study applicable in other places.

2. CONTEXT AND CHALLENGES

Circular urbanism reconnects the location for production and consumption within a city, creating a more closed-loop system where waste profiles could be greatly reduced and where resources are being regenerated in an ongoing fashion. In today's highly globalized economy, Daegu is one example of many cities which have largely lost the local manufacturing bases which drove their growth. It relies heavily on imports for food, energy and consumer goods. This dependence on extended supply chains has left many urban centres vulnerable to disruptions, environmental damage, and economic inequality.

Figure 1:
**Total consumption footprint
of South Korea & Daegu
compared to geographical
footprint**

By localising production, circular urbanism is proposed as a way to reduce a city's ecological footprint and also to foster local resilience in the face of future resource scarcity driven by climate change.

A major challenge in enacting moves toward a circular city is of testing the feasibility of models in relation to constraints of land, natural resources, and existing population density. The studio project frames this through the "Ecological Footprint," a metric that calculates the productive land which is required to support a population's consumption and including the absorption of waste. South Korea's ecological footprint has been calculated at six global hectares (GHA) per capita, meaning that each person in South Korea requires, on average, six hectares of land to support their consumption pattern (Global Footprint Network, 2021). With a population of approximately 52 million people, South Korea's total required land area is 3,118,000 km²—more than 30 times the country's actual land area of 100,363 km² (Wikipedia Contributors, 2019) (Figure 1). This enormous discrepancy highlights the unsustainable nature of current consumption patterns in South Korea or at very least deep reliance on land outside its borders. This same condition applies in many urbanized nations around the world.

In Daegu, a city of 2.4 million people and a metropolitan area of 1,499 km² (Wikipedia Contributors, 2022), the situation is even more stark. Based on its consumption patterns, Daegu's ecological footprint is nearly 100 times larger than its physical size (Figure 2).

Figure 2:
**Land required for Daegu
 consumption as a vertical
 assemblage – compared to
 Burj Khalifa**

Achieving a circular urban model would therefore require massive reductions in consumption, radical increases in urban density, and the large-scale integration of local production into the fabric of the city, once known for extensive export production. This immense challenge limited by a wide range of factors is not insurmountable spatially and the speculative design projects developed in RMIT Architecture program demonstrate that a fully circular city might be technically and spatially possible through creative architectural and urban planning strategies.

3. CASE STUDIES

Several of the design projects explore extreme production urban models, concepts that seek to integrate all of a city's production needs—food, energy, water, consumer goods, and waste management—into its current core urban environment and land footprint. That is, a city makes everything it needs within its own boundary, but also processes all of its own waste – including CO₂e emissions. A striking example of this approach is the project "Affinity & Contradictions" by Parth Nasit and Samrakshana Suresh, which dramatically densifies Daegu to accommodate production. In this vision, the city's existing street grid and urban morphology are retained, but the overall volume of the city is increased dramatically through vertical expansion. The project proposes a megastructure that spans entire city blocks, with residential, leisure and civic spaces occupying the upper layers above industrial production facilities form the middle and lower levels.

Figure 3:
**Rendered view of "Affinity
& Contradictions" by Parth
Nasit and Samrakshana
Suresh**

Figure 4:
Sectional perspective of a
circular Daegu - Parth Nasit
and Samrakshana Suresh

This design shows that by vertically stacking a wide range of productive urban programs, it is possible to compress Daegu's physical footprint into a much smaller geographic land area. This would leave existing land for other intensive production uses and space in high rise constructions to be shared between production and living. The residential spaces at the top levels benefit from access to daylight and fresh air, while the lower layers form a manufacturing underworld, where factories, workshops, and other production facilities are housed. Despite its vertical scale, the megastructure is designed to retain the fine-grained character of Daegu's small street blocks and individual human scale, allowing the city to maintain aspects of its cultural and social identity even as its density greatly increases. The project models radical densification, with all its challenges, and views this density an essential part of the viable approach to achieving a fully circular city.

A key design question from this project is whether the intimate scale of Daegu neighbourhoods on the ground could be replicated in a high rise environment. A similar approach is taken by Gokul Rameshkumar and Krutika Shah in their project "Manufacturing In-Between," which also envisions a vertically intensified city with closely integrated urban functions.

In this design, commercial activities occupy the lower levels of buildings, industrial production facilities are housed in the middle layers, and residential spaces are located at the top. This vertical organization allows for the efficient use of space while maintaining close physical connections between different urban programs. This project analyses Daegu's existing network of small-scale manufacturing workshops which operate as a decentralized built system spread across the city.

Figure 5:
Rendered view of the upper (residential) levels of a full circular Daegu – “Manufacturing In-Between” by Gokul Rameshkumar and Krutika Shah

By scaling up this system and integrating its structure into a vertical urban fabric, Rameshkumar and Shah grapple with the proposition of Daegu moving toward self-sufficiency while also retaining its identity as a city that already supports small-scale artisans and manufacturers. So while the initial targets for volume and density increase are driven by broad estimates of consumption requirements and available land area, the success of such projects relies on the capacity to accommodate a complex network of small operators. These two projects—"Affinity & Contradictions" and "Manufacturing In-Between"—highlight the spatial possibilities of integrating production into the lived urban environment. By housing residential, commercial, and industrial functions within the same buildings or city blocks, the projects model the high density required for circular economies. While the scale of transformation proposed by these projects may seem extreme, they illustrate the challenges of creating a more circular city and which require highly innovative design solutions that prioritize verticality and the efficient use of urban space. Given the currently unsustainable model of remote production serving highly consumptive cities, then these projects provoke a conversation about the radical changes needed to move toward circular urban economies—far more efficient transport and logistical routes; far more efficient consumption and production patterns, and radical compression of urban space – all of which are urban design principles that are understood to reduce the embodied and operational carbon requirements of cities.

Similar concepts to these have been explored for cities looking to create localized, and intensive production systems to reduce their environmental impact. Almost two decades ago MVRDV published "Farmax: Excursions on Density" as a design speculation (Firm, 2006). Now cities are making real plans toward such goals. The city of Amsterdam has implemented several initiatives aimed at a circular economy, reducing waste and increasing local production capacity. Amsterdam's "Circular 2020-2025" strategy emphasizes the importance of reusing materials, of reducing waste, and of promoting local production to achieve a more sustainable urban economy (Amsterdam, 2020). The project has the ambitious but real goals of halving raw material use by 2030 and being fully circular by 2050. Another example of such moves are the urban farming initiatives in the city of Singapore, where vertical farms and rooftop gardens are being developed to provide local food production within the city's dense urban core. Singapore's '30 by 30' target aims to produce 30 percent of its own nutritional needs by 2030 (Tham, 2024). These projects, while not as extensive as the speculative designs proposed for Daegu, demonstrate that elements of circular urbanism are already being implemented in cities around the world, and their potential impact on decarbonisation efforts.

The two key ingredients to make a circular city possible, high density and high levels of functional mixing have been extensively studied in a number of locations. Some of the highest density urban fabric built in Europe was at the end of the 19th century in the cities of Barcelona and Paris. In a period after the introduction of the elevator to buildings and before the completion of metropolitan subway systems, the model of living in an apartment and walking to a factory, drove very high density and the necessary colocation of production and work with living. It is of course obvious that cities achieved a profile much closer to circular in the past than they do now, just as their carbon footprint was much lower for similar reasons. Rather than see a speculation on circularity as utopian it is reasonable to view the current global models as an unsustainable aberration to urban models. The technologies and regulatory mindsets have generally mitigated against this spatial integration. Transport systems built into planning systems have dispersed populations and separated them from their place of work. Once decoupled, it was a relatively easy step to further dislocate production to anywhere on the globe. It is clear that the tactics of a circular urbanism run contrary to most of the paradigms of modern city planning, and therefore designing decarbonisation requires a radical rethinking of urbanism.

4. FINDINGS

Despite the technical and spatial possibilities demonstrated by these projects, questions remain on whether a circular city is desirable or even necessary. One could argue that the radical density increases required to achieve a circular economy could lead to undesirable living conditions, invoking dystopian megastructures which sacrifice quality of life for a smaller ecological footprint. The "Manufacturing Daegu" studio designs address these questions by composing a human scale of the city – that is small scale within a larger structure, even in the most densely populated areas. The projects propose urban environments which are cognisant of liveability. Daylight, green space, and social infrastructure are integrated into the designs of these very large structures. The projects exist to speculate on a city that is self-sufficient but also remains a desirable and sociable place to live.

The potential for Daegu to serve as a test case for circular urbanism has potential implications for other cities which all face similar challenges. Highly developed urban centres around the world are grappling with resource depletion, environmental degradation, economic inequality and social isolation. Many are looking for ways to create more sustainable and resilient urban economies. Daegu's historic reliance on factory based manufacturing and its current status as a regional hub in South Korea, makes it wellpositioned to experiment with new models of urban production.

Figure 6:
**Typological study of vertical
production facilities**

Successful circular urbanism models proposed for "Manufacturing Daegu" might contain principles or form a model for other cities seeking to reduce their ecological footprint and foster local economic resilience.

One should be wary though of the limits of replicability in urban models, particularly those laid on existing urban fabric. Open studies such as this are important in as many locations as possible for this reason. While preceding designs elsewhere may offer principles for Daegu; the testing of a particular urban location broadens the evidence base of such models, but also recognises the unique and original situation of each urban environment tested.

The speculative design projects developed in the "Manufacturing Daegu" studio offer spatial models and describe the conditions for a fully circular city that might be achievable with particular architectural and urban planning strategies. By radically increasing its urban density and integrating production facilities into the city's core, Daegu could move toward a self-sufficient urban environment capable of producing its essential resources within its own municipal boundaries. The vision of a circular city represents a response to some of the most pressing challenges facing urban environments, and reverses the tendencies of urban development to expand footprints, and outsource production offshore. The role of these projects is not to prove the economic viability of a circular economy but rather to test the spatial conditions which might serve those goals. While the scale of change is very significant, the projects from the studio demonstrate that with intelligent design strategies, cities like Daegu can at least be imagined in a transition to circular urbanism models. These models would sustain a more resilient economic and urban environment.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The two principles of reducing the lived land footprint (urban density) and of bringing production closer to consumption are the key spatial ingredients for moving toward a circular city. Daegu could become a model for other cities around the world, showing that it is possible to create an urban future where production and consumption are intensely interwoven and integrated into the urban fabric. These strategies are essential to decarbonising cities and need to be tested in as many urban arenas as possible. The role of design speculations are, however, specific to a context and complimentary to other feasibility modelling, whether it be financial, carbon based or regulatory.

The limits of a design speculation are important to recognise. These are intended to provoke a counter-factual and in this case, counter the global tendency of dispersal and functional zoning so prevalent in cities regulated by urban planning.

They ask such questions as: What pre-conditions are spatially necessary for a circular economy city? Or, more simply: What might a city look like pursuing such goals? Such projects ask also: would the radical change in density be unacceptable or would it produce other side effect benefits? Could it be that much greater density and functional mixity is beneficial even without circular economies? The approach of a design speculation assumes that partial success is useful. While it works toward the logical extension of an idea or target, it realises two that implementing change in cities is incremental, partial and contingent.

Moving on a vector away from the city which is highly dispersed and where functions are isolated from each other is beneficial, even if at a lesser degree.

Reducing the physical footprint of a city and rethinking that city's relationship with their own consumption footprint are well established paths to de-carbonising efforts. They are the variables most open to contributions from urban design. The global need to reduce ecological footprints and to create more resilient cities drives interest in the concept of circular urbanism. Testing and modelling these aims through design studies in as many specific contexts as possible presents a form of map, complimentary with other knowledges toward the destination of a de-carbonised city.

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